

A Possible Survival of an Archaic Term in Modern German

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Of all current Germanic languages, only English seems to have retained both *ale* and *beer* in reference to the drink brewed from malted grain. The other West Germanic languages have only the equivalent of *beer*; the word *ale* (i.e. its equivalent) seems to have disappeared. The North Germanic languages, in contrast, have only cognates of the word *ale*; here, the word *beer* (i.e. its Norse equivalents) seems to have vanished or never became established.

Yet there appears to be a survival of the 'ale' lexeme in West Germanic outside English. This is a somewhat hidden survival, which has come to be interpreted in a quite different way. The reference is to the element *alt-* in the compound noun *Altbier*.

A brief note on the history of beer brewing

For centuries, beer (or what one could call 'beer') was brewed using wild yeasts. These, given the right conditions, fermented on the top of the liquid. This method is still in use today, but it has many risks, as there is no way of completely controlling which yeast starts the fermentation. Domestic strains of yeast have been developed to avoid this problem. The real revolution in beer brewing occurred in the 19th century (it appears), when a method of fermentation at lower temperatures was developed. In this, the yeast drops to the bottom of the liquid, resulting in the terminology of 'top-fermented' and 'bottom-fermented' beer. In modern times, top-fermented beers are referred to in English as 'ale', while bottom-fermented beers are referred to as 'beer'.¹ There are individual styles of all of these. In Germany, there are two main types of top-fermented beer, *Altbier* and *Weizen* (wheat beer, so called because a proportion of wheat malt is mixed with the barley malt). More localised top-fermented brews also exist, such as *Kölsch* in Cologne and environs. Bottom-fermented beers are generally *Pilsener* beers (named after the city of Pilsen in Bohemia, where a Bavarian brewer first made the style famous); other styles include 'export', 'March beer' (*Märzen*) and, in Bavaria, *Helles*, which simply means a light-coloured beer as opposed to a *Dunkles*, which is a darker coloured brew.

The significant thing here is the designation *Altbier*.

Altbier – hitherto suggested etymologies

There are two main etymological derivations in circulation. One derives the element *alt-* from Latin *altus* 'high, deep', supposedly because the fermentation takes place 'on high'. This is clearly a nonce motivation at best; it makes little sense in the context of brewing. In particular, it implies a contrast or opposition to 'low', in other words, to bottom fermentation. But prior to the 19th century, the only method of brewing was by top fermentation, so it is highly improbable that such a contrast would have existed, let alone been designated. A suggestion that, because Lat. *altus* is supposedly derived from the verb *alō* 'feed, nourish, raise (of young)', this might serve as the motivation for the designation is even more clearly a nonce explanation, especially in view of the justified doubt that the Latin lexemes are etymologically connected.²

The other suggestion is simply that *Altbier*, as a top-fermented style, reflects an older type of brewing compared to the more recent introduction of bottom fermentation.

But there is a problem with this second derivation. The element *alt-* in modern German does not have the meaning 'old-fashioned'. It simply means 'old, greater in age (as a comparison)', very much as the English lexeme *old*. The word 'altmodisch' (old-fashioned) means a 'Mode' (fashion) that is 'alt' (old, of an earlier time). 'Altmetall' is simply 'old metal, scrap metal'; in compounds such as *Altbundeskanzler* it means 'former'. In the area of foodstuffs and drinks, it hardly appears at all. One exception is *altbacken*, which means primarily 'stale', as in *altbackenes Brot* 'stale bread'; in a metaphorical sense *altbacken* is used to express what is called 'dowdy, frumpy' in English. Certainly

1 The term *ale* originally referred to an unhopped beverage; from about 1700 ales were regularly hopped, and so the terms '*ale*' and '*beer*' became more or less synonymous. Cf. *The Cambridge World History Of Food*, Vol. 1, pp. 619 and 622.

2 Thus given in Walde/Hofmann, *Lateinisches Etymologisches Wörterbuch* s.v. *alō*; against this, see M. de Vaan, *Etymological Dictionary of Latin and the Other Italic Languages* Leiden 2008, s.v. *altus*.

alt- would not have a positive meaning with reference to beer. Its basic meaning in reference to food and drink is 'no longer fresh, old'. This might indicate that *alt-* in *Altbier* is not what it seems.

'Unorganic dentals' in German

One other clue might lie in the presence of the dental clusile in *alt-*. If this really is the lexeme 'old', then there is no question as to the presence of this consonant; it is part of the stem. But is another explanation possible?

In German, there is a series of lexemes which have a so-called 'unorganic' or 'excrecent'³ *t* or *d*, i.e. there is no etymological explanation for the presence of this consonant, and historically there are older forms without it. The following is a list⁴ of such lexemes (which does not aspire to being complete):

- with -t

allenthalben, Axt, Damast, dickicht, eigentlich, einst, flehentlich, gelegentlich, geflissentlich, Habicht, hoffentlich, Hüfte, jemand, jetzt, Morast, namentlich, nebst, Obst, öffentlich, ordentlich, Papst, Palast, Predigt, Saft, Sekt, selbst, Sint(flut), sonst, Werft, wesentlich, wissentlich, wöchentlich.

- with -d

dutzend, irgend, jemand, niemand, nirgend, weiland.

Others exist dialectally, e.g. *anderst* (standard *anders*), *ebent* (standard *eben*).

The thing all of these appear to have in common is that the final -t/-d was added sometime during the five centuries between 1100 and 1600 AD. For instance, *Sekt* 'champagne, sparkling wine' is derived from French (*vin*) *sec*, as is English *sack*. The German word is recorded in 1647 as *Seck*, and by 1663 it appears as *Sect*.⁵ The source of the final dental clusile is unknown.

The word for 'axe' in OHG is *ackus*, documented at around 800 AD. In Old Saxon we have *ackus*, and in MHG we see *ackes*. In Middle Low German we find *exe*, *ēxe*, *ekse*, *ēkse*, in Middle Dutch *aex*, Mod. Du. *aaks*, *aks*, while Old English has *æx*, *aex*, *æces*, Old Norse *øx*, *ax*, and Gothic *aqizi*. These are all related to Lat. *ascia* and clearly none of them show an excrecent -t. This latter begins to appear in this lexeme in traces in the 13th century.⁶

Morast and *Werft* are late arrivals, appearing first in the course of the 17th century, with *Werft* first showing the excrecent -t in the early 18th century.⁷

Wesentlich and *wissentlich* are derived, of course, from *Wesen* and *Wissen*, respectively. The adjectives display this -t not as an 'excrecence', but rather as an insertion, very probably a simple phonetic development of the transfer of articulation from the voiced alveolar continuant -*n*- to the voiced lateral dental -*l*-. Possibly the cause was at first perceptual, with language learners (i.e. children) interpreting this consonantal cluster *-*nl*- as -*ntl*-. The same would apply to *eigentlich*, *flehentlich*, *gelegentlich*, *geflossentlich*, *hoffentlich*, *namentlich*, *öffentlich*, *ordentlich*, and *wöchentlich*.

This would, however, not explain those cases of -t/-d in final position. This phenomenon remains something of a puzzle.

Alt or *alt*?

Nevertheless, it is now possible to view the element -*alt* in a different way, namely, as a reinterpretation of something different. Let us assume, *argumenti causa*, that the Germanic lexeme **alup* 'ale' did survive through the Middle and Modern High German periods. It would have become MHG **ale*, as the bisyllabic lexeme **alup* would have lost its dental clusile in final position⁸ in accordance with the sound laws governing final consonants in Germanic. This putative MHG **ale* would likely have suffered the further loss of -*e* in Modern German⁹, resulting in a lexeme **al*. This could have taken on the excrecent -t, thus resulting in a homonym of *alt* 'old'. Later, to distinguish the one from the other, **alt* 'ale' might have been attached to -*bier* 'beer', and at some

3 A term used by J. Wright in his *Historical German Grammar*, Oxford ca. 1907.

4 Wright, *Historical German Grammar* § 272.

5 Pfeifer W. et al., *Etymologisches Wörterbuch des Deutschen*, Deutscher Taschenbuch Verlag, Munich, 2nd printing 1997.

6 Pfeifer W. et al., *Etymologisches Wörterbuch des Deutschen*.

7 Pfeifer et al., op.cit. FN 4.

8 Cf. *inter alia* Krahe/Meid, *Germanische Sprachwissenschaft I*, p. 126.

9 Wright, op.cit. (FN 2), § 171 1.

point could well have ceased to occur as an independent lexeme, leading to the confusion again with *alt* 'old'. The basic point of departure was a disyllabic with a short-vowel stem, in any case. This is speculative, of course, and one might object that, in the list above of lexemes with excrescent -t/-d, none otherwise has -l in final position. Indeed, Wright op.cit. § 272 says explicitly that 'In NHG. an excrescent **t** has often been developed after **n**, and spirants, rarely after other consonants.' But this need not be a problem; /l/ is not phonetically far distant from /n/ in German and other languages, so it is at least thinkable that an excrescent /t/ may have been added in this case.

With this in mind, it can be argued that we see here the survival of a term otherwise unattested in Modern High German. Further possible support may be found in the existence of a lexeme *Öl* with the meaning 'beer, ale' in Bavarian ('Bavarian' understood here as the dialect continuum encompassing Southern Bavaria and Austria east of the Tirol). But this is more likely to be either a fairly recent borrowing from Scandinavia or a transfer of the term as used in the Catholic Church (extreme unction, anointing of the sick); this latter is indicated by the dialect and slang expressions '*fett sein*' and '*im Öl sein*', both meaning 'drunk'.

One reason for the lexeme **alub* to have had such a limited transmission could be that it was originally associated with pre-Christian religious practices. E. H. Antonsen basically agrees with the idea first put forward by Edgar Polomé that the lexeme **alub* could be derived from a stem which may also be seen in Greek ἀλύω, ἀλύσσω, Latvian *aluôt(iês)*, Latvian *āluôtiês*, Hittite *alwanza-*. According to this, **alub* would originally have been 'that which induces the ecstatic state' (in cult ritual).¹⁰ The lexeme *beer* (and the German cognate *Bier*) could possibly be derived from a late or Middle Lat. *biber*, indicating a monastic origin.¹¹

The survival of *ale* in English might be connected with the survival of an unusual number of pre-Christian place-names (e.g. *Wednesbury*, and indeed the day of the week *Wednesday*, together with the other days of the week: *Tuesday*, *Thursday*, *Friday*) in England. In Germany there are far fewer; Christianisation in the continental Germanic areas was often very warlike (see Charlemagne and the Saxons) and seems to have driven pre-Christian religious beliefs even further into the margins of society.¹² It is worth pointing out that the conversion of the continental Germans was later than that of the Anglo-Saxons. In Scandinavia, Christianisation was relatively late, which could account for the survival of the lexeme **alub* there.

We are left, then, with a possibly quite archaic survival in German of a lexeme thought to have been lost in that language. While the explanation offered here may seem improbable, it has at least the merit of some semantic credibility, which is lacking in the etymologies hitherto proffered.

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10 Cf. E. H. Antonsen, *Runes and Germanic Linguistics*, Berlin/New York 2002, pp. 196-200.

11 Pfeifer et al., op.cit. FN 4., s.v. *Bier*.

12 See C. Lecouteux, *Eine Welt im Abseits. Zur niederen Mythologie und Glaubenswelt des Mittelalters*. Dettelbach 2000.